

A portable VNA-based system for grid impedance measurements

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Abstract — Conducted emissions are strongly dependent on the impedance of the grid and EUT, to measure in line conditions. A portable system is presented (verified against calibration standards) together with results of tests for probes non-linearity.

Keywords — electromagnetic interference, impedance measurement, network analyzers, power systems, probes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The behaviour of the grid impedance feeding a specific equipment is a relevant element of the assessment of conducted emissions from many viewpoints. For reproducibility the CISPR 16-2-1 [1] for common-mode (CM) conducted emissions indicates the Line Impedance Stabilizing Network (LISN) impedance curve and the prescribed maximum deviation. The grid impedance values $Z_{mains,CM}$ may vary significantly from the reference $Z_{LISN,CM}$ causing correspondingly a change of the voltage measured on the latter. Similarly, the larger the feeding impedance, the lower the conducted current emission will be. However, in modern distribution grids the differential-mode (DM) impedance is becoming more and more relevant as the coupling element for significant DM disturbance caused by a wide range of devices: lighting and light dimming [2], switched-mode power supplies [3], power converters for e.g. photovoltaic [4] or vehicle charging [5] applications. This is particularly evident in the recently investigated supraharmonic (SH) frequency interval (2–150 kHz).

Regarding the SH frequency interval, although there are suggestions for LISN designs in CISPR 16-1-2 [6], EN 50065-1 [7] and IEC 61000-4-7 [8], the impedance values for this range are not well stabilized around 50 Ω . So, there is no reliable corresponding LISN for the DM part of the grid impedance, $Z_{mains,DM}$, that is in general subject to wider variations, following the variation of the output impedance of actively controlled power converters [9] and the continuous reconfiguration of the network, as caused by connections and disconnection of the loads [10].

Methods for the non-intrusive measurement of the grid impedance in live conditions are therefore extremely useful and have already been investigated in a few occasions in the past. Such methods may be divided into two broad categories: Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) based methods, using the 2-probe configuration [11] and providing the sought Z_g (either

CM or DM) after the calibration. Time-domain methods, using a more direct approach that measures the voltage and the flowing current at the measured port (usually applying Fourier-based analysis supported by post-processing to remove outliers and interfered components) [12].

Any EUT can be modelled as a combination of a voltage source and an internal impedance (Thevenin equivalent) and this model can be used to analyse the conducted emissions and reduce the uncertainty arising from the test circuit impedance. The reference and the actual test circuits (corresponding to an “ideal setup” and the in-situ conditions, respectively) are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. DM (a) reference and (b) actual circuit models for conducted emissions in the SH frequency interval.

Measurement of the actual test circuit DM impedance ($Z_{EUT,DM} + Z_{setup,DM} + Z_{mains,DM}$) and the live mains DM impedance ($Z_{mains,DM}$) is necessary to establish a correlation between the actual test circuit DM current I_{DM} in (1) and the reference test circuit DM current $I_{DM,ref}$ in (2).

$$I_{DM} = \frac{V_{EUT,DM}}{Z_{EUT,DM} + Z_{setup,DM} + Z_{mains,DM}} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{DM,ref} = \frac{V_{EUT,DM}}{Z_{EUT,DM} + Z_{setup,DM} + Z_{LISN,DM}} \quad (2)$$

After the quantification of the actual test circuit impedance and the mains impedance in live conditions, the successive step is to measure I_{DM} by means of a suitable current clamp. I_{DM} can then be converted to the reference circuit current by a conversion factor, $K_{I,DM}$ given in (3).

$$K_{I,DM} = \frac{I_{DM,ref}}{I_{DM}} = \frac{Z_{EUT,DM} + Z_{setup,DM} + Z_{mains,DM}}{Z_{EUT,DM} + Z_{setup,DM} + Z_{LISN,DM}} \quad (3)$$

Conducted emissions for a LISN reference case, $V_{DM,ref}$ can be calculated by using the LISN differential impedance $Z_{LISN,DM}$:

$$V_{DM,ref} = |Z_{LISN,DM}| |I_{DM,ref}| \quad (4)$$

If the currents are measured with quasi-peak or average detectors using a frequency selective receiver, $V_{DM,ref}$ can directly be used to compare with the CISPR emission limits. Correction of mains impedance effects may be useful to harmonize emission results obtained in different environments and make them comparable between each other.

It is important to keep in mind that all values are complex numbers, so if the scalar values are considered as indicated in (4), worst-case emission values are obtained. A time-domain measurement followed by FFT post-processing will yield vectorial values and thus more realistic emission results.

Whereas an uncertainty estimate has been already considered in laboratory conditions [13], the on-site application requires that some additional elements are taken into account. For all methods a significant source of uncertainty is the non-linear behaviour of the current probes as caused by the varying intensity of the fundamental and in general low-frequency current, possibly approaching saturation. A second external uncertainty contribution comes from the effect of superposed noise that is commonplace for distribution grids, especially in the presence of switched-mode power conversion units. Both problems have been rarely considered in the literature, but are quite relevant for a successful realization applicable to a wide range of residential and industrial environments.

The paper is thus structured as follows: Section II provides a description of the VNA-based measuring method and of the portable system; Section III describes the test setup and reports the results of the characterization of the portable system and of current probes non-linearity.

II. VNA-ORIENTED MEASURING EQUIPMENT/SETUP

The measurement of an unknown impedance using a VNA, see Fig. 2, is carried out by applying a driving signal from the port 1 (coupled by means of an injecting probe) and the resulting current is measured by a receiving probe connected to port 2.

Fig. 2. Two-current-probe setup used for comparison of the measuring systems and assessment of uncertainty caused by probe saturation and noise.

The unknown impedance Z_x can be expressed with the following equation:

$$Z_x = K \frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} - Z_{setup} \quad (5)$$

where K is the frequency dependent coupling factor, Z_{setup} is the impedance of the wire loop, V_{p1} and V_{p2} are the voltages on port 1 and port 2 of the VNA, respectively.

The voltage ratio V_{p1}/V_{p2} can be expressed with the measured S parameters as:

$$\frac{V_{p1}}{V_{p2}} = \frac{S_{11} + 1}{S_{21}} \quad (6)$$

By combining (5) and (6), Z_x is expressed in terms of the measured S parameters and the Z_{setup} :

$$Z_x = K \frac{S_{11} + 1}{S_{21}} - Z_{setup} \quad (7)$$

The quantities K and Z_{setup} are the two unknowns to fix by at least two independent measurements, achieved by replacing impedance Z_x with known impedance standards, i.e. an Open or a Short circuit and a Known Impedance. Usually the Short is preferable, as the influence of parasitic terms is more under control; it is noted that the Known Impedance does not need to be a matched impedance.

$$Z_{Short} = K \left(\frac{S_{11} + 1}{S_{21}} \right)_{Sh} - Z_{setup} \quad (8)$$

$$Z_{KnownZ} = K \left(\frac{S_{11} + 1}{S_{21}} \right)_{K.Z} - Z_{setup} \quad (9)$$

In this context, a portable live impedance measurement system was designed, developed and validated, which made internal current probes, supporting also the use of external probes by means of internal RF switches (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Design of the portable impedance measurement system: (a) high-level diagram, (b) photo

The overall dimensions are 43 cm (L) × 28 cm (W) × 15 cm (H) with a weight of about 6 kg, which make the system portable.

The portable system is connected to a PC through a USB port. A software solution was also developed by using the ANSI C language in the LabWindows™/CVI platform to operate with the device and collect all the data in tabular and graphical form. The two tabs of the main window are shown in Fig. 4. The software is able to control the portable device, perform live impedance measurements through S parameters for short, open, reference and unknown impedance conditions and to ultimately calculate magnitude and phase data of the unknown impedance along with the overall loop and cable impedance values.

III. TEST SETUP AND RESULTS

The portable system was verified against an Agilent E5061B VNA [15] with the 2-probe setup of Fig. 2, using a set of known/unknown impedances: Rosenberger 50 Ω N-type

incorporates an Omicron Bode 100 VNA [14] and two home-termination, Maury mismatch termination, 150 Ω coupling-decoupling network and 100 pF capacitor.

The results for two selected tests (the 50 Ω reference and the mismatched termination) are shown in Fig. 5 for both magnitude and phase of the unknown impedance Z_x measured from 10 kHz to 30 MHz.

Further tests were carried out and they are the verification of (i) the non-linearity of the probes approaching supposed saturation values for the linked ampere-turns, and (ii) the effect of a deteriorated signal-to-noise ratio due to added external noise.

The test setup was built around the two-probe setup shown in Fig. 2, adding a 42-turn coil to drive a large bias current into the probes (“bias coil”) and a 3-turn coil to apply an arbitrary amount of noise by means of a function generator (“noise coil”). The probes selected for the tests were the two probes with the largest saturation point available and of different construction, so with quite a different size and probe factor: FCC-73 [16] and EZ-17 [17].

The geometry of the bias coil was the result of a trade-off between opposing requisites: (i) compactness to fit into the other probes window, (ii) large number of turns to reduce the amount of external bias current to feed, and (iii) self-resonance due to unavoidable stray capacitance. The first two requisites were relatively easy to handle finding a compromise in the built 42 turns. The third requisite instead turned out to be unmanageable by design, as a self-resonance was always present in the frequency range of interest (9 kHz to 30 MHz, possibly going down to 2 kHz). The decision was taken to include the bias coil in the setup during the calibration with care of terminating it exactly in the same feeding conditions when a bias current is applied. To this aim not only the connection, but the output impedance conditions of the power supplies turned out to be relevant. The same was repeated for the noise coil having connected the function generator turned on, but at negligible output signal.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Screenshots of the software developed for the live impedance measurements with the portable device (a) measurement parameters, (b) measurement.

Fig. 5. Verification of the performance of the portable system vs. the Agilent E5061B VNA for (a,b) Roseberg 50 Ω reference and (c,d) Maury mismatch reference.

A. Bias current effect and saturation

The tested bias current values were 2, 3, 4 and 5 A DC (that multiplied by 42 turns bring to 84, 126, 168 and 210 At), applied in turn to each of the two probes. The results consist of measured impedance curves referred to the 50 Ω calibration standard for the conditions of “no bias current applied” and the various bias current levels previously listed. In the case of the FCC 73, due to its large gain, it was judged opportune to add a test level at lower current, namely 1A.

The results can be seen in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. The effect of the bias current is more pronounced at lower frequency, being negligible at higher frequency. It is likely that this results, or is at least promoted, by the Bode 100 VNA lower dynamic range, which makes it more susceptible to current probes non-linear behaviour. The effect of bias current below saturation point on impedance measurements can be minimal if the dynamic range of the VNA is sufficiently large (this is a point to check in order to define a requirement on the instrumentation to use).

Fig. 6. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. bias current for the EZ-17: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

Fig. 7. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. bias current for the FCC-73: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

B. External noise and reduced signal-to-noise ratio

The noise coil was instead fed with 1.0, 3.2, 6.0 and 10.0 Vpp of white noise amplitude, with the generator set for white noise over the bandwidth up to 30 MHz. An offline calculation

was carried out to estimate the power spectral density and to compare with spectra measured with the E5061B, finding a very good correspondence. The 1 Vpp level led to no visible effect, for which during post-processing only the results of the 3 largest levels were retained and are displayed in the following.

It is evident that at high frequency the largest effect is caused by the largest noise applied (10 Vpp). The situation is more confused below 100 kHz, where in some instances the reference case seems the one with the largest spread. This disordered behaviour may still be caused by the lower performance at low frequency of the Bode 100 compared to a full fledged laboratory VNA.

Fig. 8. Impedance curves of the 50 Ω reference vs. external noise for the FCC-73: (a) magnitude, (b) phase.

IV. CONCLUSION

The problem of the accurate measurement of the grid impedance in live conditions has been discussed, presenting a portable system realized at Tubitak and using an Omicron Bode 100 device with internal probes and RF switches for connection of external probes.

Besides the influence of the Bode 100 performance in a VNA perspective, what was identified as a relevant point in a live measurement perspective is the operation of current probes with respect to two non-idealities: system noise and

non-linearity as caused by large fundamental current intensity. To this aim two probes were selected with a similar and large declared saturation point, in the order of 300 Apk. Rather than testing the saturation point, the interest was in the behavior and the resulting uncertainty for increasing fundamental current intensity. This was simulated using an auxiliary coil fed by a DC power supply; the coil was included in the calibration to compensate the loading effect and consequential resonances induced on the test circuit. Similarly noise was applied with another smaller coil fed by a signal generator and also this coil had to be included in the calibration of the setup. In both cases, as expected, higher intensity causes larger spread of measured values with different behavior at low and high frequency. A concomitant factor may be the limited dynamic range and performance of the Bode 100, so that tests will be carried out also with the Agilent E5061B VNA, representing the other end of the performance range.

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